

**DIGITAL BUSINESS TRANSFORMATION IN THE TOURISM
INDUSTRY**

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Annotation: The tourism industry encompasses a lot of different sectors. From transportation services such as airline- and railway companies and car rental services to the production and distribution of products for leisure activities such as paper or digital tour guides and translators. Simply said, the tourism industry can be defined by the services, infrastructures, and products that make leisure travel possible, from start to finish.

Keywords: technology, tourism industry, artificial intelligence, augmented, virtual reality, and blockchain technology, online reservation, digital tour guides, smart destinations.

The significant decrease in mobility caused by the coronavirus pandemic has resulted in a major drop in tourism leading to a decline in the travel services business. Lockdowns and social distancing measures have resulted in sharp drops in the use of tourist services, which had previously been consistent and even growing. As many elements of tourism have been forced to slow down, the necessity and demand for innovative technology in the tourism industry have never been greater. Even though the widespread use of the COVID-19 vaccines is creating a safer environment for traveling, many countries are still enforcing strict regulations and limitations regarding traveling tourists.¹

Technologies in the tourism industry

How does digital transformation helps affect the tourism industry? When you're planning a trip, there's a lot that needs to be done to make sure your trip goes as smoothly as possible. You probably start with finding a destination, which can be far away or close to home. Whereas twenty years ago, you would probably drop by a travel agency near you, you can now find, book, and pay for your entire journey with a few clicks and swipes on your smartphone, tablet, or laptop. You can book your train tickets to the airport, your flight to your

¹ Ziyadin, S., Koryagina, E., Grigoryan, T., Tovma, N., Ismail, G.Z. International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology, 10(1), 998-1010 (2019).

destination, and your hotel for your stay in minutes. Once you arrive at your destination, you can find the best-rated restaurants near you from a wide selection of review platforms, websites, and applications.²

In the past, you had spent hours going through loads of confirmation papers and forms to just book a single ticket, and then we're not even speaking of the time it took to wait in endless queues at the check-in desks at hotels, airports, car rental counters, and more. The reason this took so long is because most, if not all procedures were done manually. While your name and personal information now pop up on a screen, retrieved from a database, it previously required a thorough search through years of paper documentation, which were easy to forget, lose, or even forge. The emergence of digital transformation technologies, from process automation to data analytics, has sped up these processes immensely, and that's just one small part of the digitization of the tourism industry.³

Benefits & examples

The use of technologies such as the 'Internet of Things,' location-based services, [artificial intelligence](#), augmented and [virtual reality](#), and [blockchain](#) technology has resulted in a more appealing, efficient, inclusive, and economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable tourism offer than before. It has also helped in providing travelers with optimal destinations by implementing technologies that can detect seasonal and situational influences in specific tourist locations, also known as smart destinations. For example, a trip booking platform making use of these kinds of algorithms will likely not recommend you a vacation spot where the weather conditions are poor or where they predict overcrowdedness.⁴

What are the examples of digital transformation in tourism? Here are some more beneficial influences and examples of technology on the travel and tourism industry:

Smart travel for a better experience

A unified smart travel model – one that encompasses smart visas, borders, security processes, and infrastructure – will revolutionize tourism in the same way that the smartphone transformed telecommunications and media. Passengers can purchase tickets and check in online, have their boarding passes

² Ziyadin, S., Suiubayeva, S., Kabasheva, N., & Moldazhanov, M. Economic Annals -XXI, 163(1-2), 35-40. (10) (2017). DOI: 10.21003/ea.V163-07

³ Beyzhanova, A., Mamyrbekov, A., Umarov, I., Orazymbetova, A., Khairullaeva, A. E3S Web of Conferences (2019). DOI: 10.1051/e3sconf/201913504023

⁴ Watkins, M., Ziyadin, S., Imatayeva, A., Kurmangalieva, A., Blembayeva, A. Digital tourism as a key factor in the development of the economy. Economic Annals-XXI, 169(1-2), 40-45 (2018).

on their cellphones, pass through automated clearance gates, and even authenticate their boarding passes electronically to board planes thanks to the interconnectedness of all these tools. These methods greatly improve travel convenience as well as security and safety.⁵

Job creation

Because the future of travel is focused on digitization, tourism jobs will require specific technical skills to efficiently execute and manage smart travel services. The greatest societal impact of digital change in tourism might be on the industry's workforce, which accounts for one out of every ten jobs on a global scale. The automation of processes impacts jobs currently done manually, either changing them or making them obsolete. However, because it is expected that the tourism sector will grow even larger, digitally-enabled growth will create many new job opportunities.⁶

Smart destinations

A smart location has a technology, innovation, sustainability, accessibility, and inclusion strategy in place throughout the entire tourism cycle: before, during, and after the trip. A smart destination considers both locals and visitors when planning tourism, taking into account multilingualism, cultural factors, and seasonality. Smart destinations offer a seamless experience for tourists while sustainably managing local resources by continuously and correctly monitoring, integrating, and analyzing data for efficient decision-making, prioritization, and anticipation of difficulties.⁷

Digital tour guides

Digital tour guides allow tourists to enhance their journey by having online and offline access to information about their location on their smartphone or tablet. From community recommendations to location-based audio guides, a digital tour guide is made to make traveling an easier and more exciting experience. Besides existing tour guides available on the internet and in app stores, locals can also choose to become tour guides themselves by creating their custom tours on several online platforms.⁸

⁵ Daribaeva A.K, Shulenbaeva F.A Aktualnye voprosy razvitiya turizma v respublike Kazahstan. Ekonomika i biznes teoriya i praktika(5), 208-212, (2016).

⁶ Ziyadin, S., & Takhtaeva, R. Trends and problems in tourism development on the territory of Eastern Kazakhstan region. Actual Problems of Economics,, (9), 232- 236. (2014).

⁷ Ziyadin, S., Litvishko, O., Dubrova, M., Smagulova, G., Suyunchaliyeva, M. Diversification tourism in the conditions of the digitalization. International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology. 10(2), 1055-1070 (2019).

⁸ Ziyadin, S., Madiyarova, A., Blembayeva, A. International tourism as a factor of world development, Proceedings of the 32nd International Business Information Management Association Conference, IBIMA

Online reservation & check-ins

Whereas before the emergence of the internet and smartphones, we had to stand in endless lines at the airport to obtain and check in our boarding passes. Nowadays, we can do this all from the comfort of our couch before even leaving for the airport. Especially in times of a global pandemic, this is a useful solution that increases the possibility of social distancing at airports during the check-in process.⁹

Online communities

Online communities have become major players in the tourism industry. When looking for a hotel or restaurant at our destination, we can instantly read through the review section to find out if it's worth a visit. In that sense, one could say that these communities have become a new type of tour guide, collectively recommending the best spots in and around your travel destination.

Travel safety guidelines

In times of a global pandemic, governments all over the world have installed specific regulations regarding travel and tourism in their countries. For example, some countries only allow vaccinated travelers, while others don't allow any tourism at all. Because the situation is constantly changing, these regulations are changing too. To know exactly where you stand, governments all over the world provide tourists and citizens with digital information platforms that provide users with real-time insights into the current situation regarding rules and regulations in their country. This also includes warning levels regarding risks of terrorism and/or environmental disasters such as floods or forest fires.

References:

1. Ziyadin, S., Koryagina, E., Grigoryan, T., Tovma, N., Ismail, G.Z. International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology, 10(1), 998-1010 (2019).
2. Ziyadin, S., Suiubayeva, S., Kabasheva, N., & Moldazhanov, M. Economic Annals -XXI, 163(1-2), 35-40. (10) (2017). DOI: 10.21003/ea.V163-07
3. Beyzhanova, A., Mamyrbekov, A., Umarov, I., Orazymbetova, A., Khairullaeva, A. E3S Web of Conferences (2019). DOI: 10.1051/e3sconf/201913504023
4. Watkins, M., Ziyadin, S., Imatayeva, A., Kurmangalieva, A., Blembayeva, A. Digital tourism as a key factor in the development of the economy. Economic Annals-XXI, 169(1-2), 40-45 (2018).

2018 - Vision 2020: Sustainable Economic Development and Application of Innovation Management from Regional expansion to Global Growth, Pages 5846-5853 (2018).

⁹ Shedenov, U., Litvishko, O., Kazbekov, B., Suyunchaliyeva, M., Kazbekova, K. Improvement of ecological tourism on the principles of sustainable economic development E3S Web of Conferences 2019.

5. Daribaeva A.K, Shulenbaeva F.A Aktualnye voprosy razvitiya turizma v respublike Kazahstan. Ekonomika i biznes teoriya i praktika(5), 208-212, (2016).
6. Ziyadin, S., & Takhtaeva, R. Trends and problems in tourism development on the territory of Eastern Kazakhstan region. Actual Problems of Economics,, (9), 232- 236. (2014).
7. Ziyadin, S., Litvishko, O., Dubrova, M., Smagulova, G., Suyunchaliyeva, M. Diversification tourism in the conditions of the digitalization. International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology. 10(2), 1055-1070 (2019).
8. Ziyadin, S., Madiyarova, A., Blembayeva, A. International tourism as a factor of world development, Proceedings of the 32nd International Business Information Management Association Conference, IBIMA 2018 - Vision 2020: Sustainable Economic Development and Application of Innovation Management from Regional expansion to Global Growth, Pages 5846-5853 (2018).
9. Shedenov, U., Litvishko, O., Kazbekov, B., Suyunchaliyeva , M., Kazbekova, K. Improvement of ecological tourism on the principles of sustainable economic development E3S Web of Conferences 2019.
10. Garifyanova Vilena I., & Galimov Almaz Mirzanurovich. Issledovanie vozmozhnostej cifrovizacii v industrii mezhdunarodnogo turizma. Kazanskij vestnik molodyh uchyonyh, 3 (2 (10)), 157-164 (2019).

